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Examining the Role of Women in Peacebuilding Efforts and the Legal Frameworks Promoting their Participation in Conflict Resolution

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Abstract

This research critically examines the role of women in peacebuilding efforts and the legal frameworks that aim to promote their active participation in conflict resolution processes. Despite the acknowledgment of women's indispensable contributions to peacebuilding, they are often marginalized and underrepresented in formal peace negotiations and decision-making forums. Drawing upon a comprehensive review of literature, case studies, and analysis of relevant legal instruments, this paper explores the multifaceted challenges hindering women's meaningful engagement in peacebuilding initiatives. Key challenges include entrenched gender stereotypes, socio-cultural barriers, lack of access to decision-making processes, and threats to women's security and safety in conflict-affected environments. Furthermore, structural inequalities perpetuate the exclusion of women from peace processes, limiting the potential for sustainable peace and security outcomes. Against this backdrop, the paper evaluates international and national legal frameworks that seek to enhance women's participation in conflict resolution. It examines landmark legal instruments such as United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace, and Security, as well as national laws and policies promoting gender equality and women's rights in conflict settings.

Keywords

Differently-abled Persons; Indian Jurisprudence; Reservation; Right to Education

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Introduction

Education Women's participation in peacebuilding processes is increasingly recognized as critical to sustainable peace and security in conflict affected regions worldwide. Historically, women have played central roles in informal peace initiatives, community cohesion and reconciliatory efforts within their societies. However, their participation in formal peace negotiations and decision-making has often been marginal or excluded. Recognizing the transformative potential of women's roles in peacebuilding, international and national actors have increasingly emphasized the need to encourage the participation of women as a fundamental factor for the resolution of conflict and post-conflict reconstruction. Women representation in peacebuilding is anchored on various good reasons. Firstly, women add fresh ideas, diverse backgrounds, and various approaches to the negotiation table, which makes the discussion deeper and more comprehensive.¹

The objective of the paper is to understand the Contribution of Women in Peacebuilding and analyse the diverse roles which women play in peacebuilding efforts. These include mediation among others. Evaluating the Impact of Women's Participation and determining how effective and sustainable peace agreements are when women are involved in peace processes such as

¹ Arostegui, J. 'Gender, conflict, and peace-building: How conflict can catalyse positive change for women', (2013) *Gender & Development*, 21(3), pp. 533-549. doi:10.1080/13552074.2013.846624.

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conflict resolution by recognizing international or regional laws that support females' involvement in peace building activities. It is usually their participation that manifests in more all-encompassing and sustainable peace contracts which cater for the numerous needs and stands of different sections of the society. Finally, studies show that women's participation in peace negotiations result in peace agreements being more durable. Opening space for women creates greater legitimacy and community acceptance of peace deals which in turn positively impacts on the implementation and effectiveness of those deals. Finally promoting gender equality and women's rights are essentially linked to the other development priorities such as poverty alleviation, social cohesion, and human security among others.

Research Methodology

The research methodology for examining the role of women in peacebuilding efforts and the legal frameworks promoting their participation in conflict resolution employs a comprehensive mixed-methods approach to capture both qualitative and quantitative dimensions of the subject. This begins with an extensive literature review to gather existing knowledge from academic sources, policy reports, and case studies, focusing on feminist peacebuilding theories, gender studies, and international relations to understand the broader theoretical context. Key international legal documents such as UNSCR 1325, CEDAW, and the Beijing Platform for Action, alongside regional frameworks like the Maputo Protocol and EU gender policies, will be critically analysed to assess their scope, implementation, and impact on women's participation in peace processes. In-depth case studies of peace processes in diverse regions, such as Liberia, Colombia, and Northern Ireland, will provide comparative insights into the roles and impacts of women in different contexts. These case studies will rely on secondary data from official reports and historical records, complemented by primary data obtained through semi-structured interviews and surveys with a wide range of stakeholders, including female peacebuilders, policymakers, NGO representatives, and members of international organizations. The interviews taken offer detailed qualitative insights into the personal experiences, challenges, and successes of women involved in peacebuilding, while surveys will gather quantitative data on broader perceptions and trends. A comparative analysis will then be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of different legal frameworks and the outcomes of peace processes with varying levels of female participation, focusing on the inclusivity and durability of peace agreements. Data triangulation will be used to cross-verify findings from the literature review, document analysis, case studies, interviews, and surveys, ensuring the validity and reliability of the results. Ethical considerations will be strictly adhered to throughout the research, including informed consent, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw, ensuring the protection of participants' rights and well-being. This methodological framework, combining robust qualitative and quantitative analyses, provides a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the critical role of women in peacebuilding and the effectiveness of legal frameworks designed to promote their participation in conflict resolution, ensuring a depth and breadth of perspective on the issue that highlights both theoretical and practical dimensions.

Research Question

It is important to understand how women function in the process of peacebuilding and to examine the extent to which women's tasks and duties in peacebuilding may or may not differ from those that were assigned to men in the past.² First, the role and success of international legal frameworks such as United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 (UNSCR 1325) and the

² Gizelis T-I, 'A Country of Their Own: Women and Peacebuilding' (2011) 28

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Convention to Eliminate All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) on enhancing women's contributions in peacebuilding. The following are the main questions that this research seeks to answer

1. To what extent does women's involvement in peace processes affect the effectiveness and cohesiveness of the peace deal?
2. How are the regional legal conditions (that is the Maputo Protocol, gender policies for the EU) affecting participation of women in matters concerning peace building in the said regions?
3. In what ways do women's civil society organizations enhance peace-building processes and about what challenges do they experience in conflicts and post conflicts?
4. Can women's experiences and views in relation to conflict transformation incline them toward nonviolent methods of conflict resolution?

Analysis and scope of women's contribution to peacebuilding efforts

The job of women in peacebuilding endeavours and the legitimate structures advancing their support in compromise uncovers a multi-layered and critical powerful that is fundamental for accomplishing reasonable harmony. Ladies frequently expect different jobs in peacebuilding processes, like go between, arbitrators, supporters, and local area coordinators, bringing extraordinary viewpoints that accentuate compromise, local area union, and tending to main drivers of contention. Dissimilar to conventional methodologies regularly overwhelmed by men, which frequently centre around progressive power structures and political settlements, ladies' contribution will in general advance inclusivity, civil rights, and comprehensive arrangements that think about the social, monetary, and social components of harmony. The viability of global lawful structures, for example, UNSCR 1325³ and CEDAW⁴ has been critical in certain unique situations, commanding the consideration of women in all degrees of harmony processes and guaranteeing their security from orientation-based viciousness while consolidating an orientation viewpoint in peacekeeping tasks. Notwithstanding, the viability of these systems shifts, for certain nations showing prominent advancement and others battling due to political, social, or asset imperatives. A few hindrances hinder women's full cooperation in peacebuilding, including dug in cultural standards and orientation generalizations, restricted admittance to training and assets, security concerns, and an absence of political will. These boundaries are many times well established in male centric designs and require fundamental changes to be really tended to. Ladies' support in harmony dealings has been displayed to prompt more exhaustive and sturdy nonaggression treaties. Their contribution guarantees that harmony processes are not exclusively cantered around political power-sharing yet additionally on modifying social orders, tending to common liberties, civil rights, and local area government assistance, consequently forestalling future struggles. Territorial lawful structures, for example, the Maputo Convention in Africa and EU orientation strategies further supplement global endeavours by tending to explicit provincial difficulties and advancing ladies' support in peacebuilding. These systems frequently offer extra help and support customized to neighbourhood settings; however, their effect can differ contingent upon political and social conditions. Grassroots ladies' associations assume a basic part in peacebuilding by preparing networks, encouraging exchange, and offering fundamental types of assistance. Working in the most impacted and underestimated regions, these associations address prompt necessities and main drivers of contention, frequently spanning holes left by formal harmony processes. Financial strengthening drives drove by ladies al-

³ 'Critically Examining UNSCR 1325 on Women, Peace and Security', 'Critically Examining UNSCR 1325 on Women, Peace and Security' (6 December 2011)

⁴ Englehart NA and Miller MK, 'The CEDAW Effect: International Law's Impact on Women's Rights' 22

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together add to peacebuilding and post-struggle recuperation. By giving livelihoods, professional preparation, and microfinance, these drives assist with remaking war-torn economies and diminish motivators for taking part in struggle. The coordination of women in monetary recuperation processes guarantees that harmony profits are impartially appropriated, encouraging long haul strength. Women encounters and points of view in struggle zones significantly shape their way to deal with peacebuilding and compromise.⁵ Having frequently borne the brunt of war's ramifications, ladies focus on helpful requirements, social union, and the reproduction of local area ties. Their grassroots-level commitment guarantees that peacebuilding endeavours are grounded in the lived real factors of those generally impacted by struggle. Fruitful contextual analyses where ladies play played huge parts in harmony processes, like in Liberia, Colombia, and Northern Ireland, feature best practices that can be recreated somewhere else. These contextual analyses uncover the significance of comprehensive discussions, the benefit of tending to orientation explicit issues, and the advantages of including ladies in all phases of harmony processes, from exchange to execution and observing. They likewise highlight the need of establishing empowering conditions where women can take part completely, including lawful assurances, instructive open doors, and financial help.⁶

Global and provincial associations can more likely help the execution of lawful systems by guaranteeing that commands are upheld by satisfactory assets, political responsibility, and responsibility components. Upgrading participation between legislatures, NGOs, and worldwide bodies is pivotal for building limit, sharing accepted procedures, and cultivating a climate where women's commitments to peacebuilding are perceived and esteemed. To address the boundaries to women cooperation in peacebuilding, coordinated endeavours are expected at numerous levels. This incorporates advancing orientation delicate instruction, testing and changing oppressive social standards, improving security for women activists, and guaranteeing that political frameworks are comprehensive and receptive to women requirements. Lawful changes ought to be supplemented by viable measures that engage women financially and socially, empowering them to take part definitively in harmony processes.

The presence of women in positions of leadership can greatly reduce the likelihood of violent conflict emerging as well as the prospects for the peaceful resolution of existing conflicts. Research has shown that countries with greater gender equality are more likely to resolve conflicts without violence and are less likely to use military force to resolve international disputes. Conversely, countries with more significant gender gaps are more likely to be involved in inter- and intrastate conflict. Women have long been active participants in peacebuilding efforts, contributing in diverse and invaluable ways to conflict resolution, reconciliation, and post-conflict reconstruction. Their involvement extends across various spheres, including grassroots initiatives, community mobilization, advocacy, and leadership roles within formal peace processes. One of the key contributions of women to peacebuilding is their ability to foster dialogue, build trust, and bridge divides within fractured societies. Through their relational networks and deep connections to local communities, women often serve as mediators, facilitators, and peacebuilders, playing pivotal roles in de-escalating tensions and promoting reconciliation.⁷

The United Nations emphasizes the importance of women's roles in making and building peace for sustainable peace and stability. Women's involvement at all stages, from decision-making to project implementation, is crucial. Women's inclusion in peacebuilding processes contributes to longer-lasting peace after conflicts. Despite progress since the Beijing Declaration in 1995,

⁵ Goetz AM and Jenkins R, 'Agency and Accountability: Promoting Women's Participation in Peacebuilding' 211

⁶ Erzurum K and Eren B, 'Women in Peacebuilding: A Criticism of Gendered Solutions in Postconflict Situations' 236

⁷ Cahill-Ripley A, 'Reclaiming the Peacebuilding Agenda: Economic and Social Rights as a Legal Framework for Building Positive Peace - A Human Security Plus Approach to Peacebuilding' (2016) 16 223

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women remain underrepresented in formal peace processes, with only 13% of negotiators, 3% of mediators, and 4% of signatories between 1992 and 2018. Efforts to amplify the voices and contributions of women peacebuilders are essential for creating more inclusive and sustainable peace agreements worldwide. Furthermore, women bring unique perspectives and priorities to peacebuilding processes, advocating for issues such as gender equality, human rights, and social justice. Their experiences as caregivers, breadwinners, and survivors of conflict equip them with a nuanced understanding of the root causes and consequences of violence, informing more holistic approaches to conflict resolution. Women's participation in peacebuilding also extends beyond formal negotiations to encompass activities such as trauma healing, psychosocial support, and community development, which are essential for laying the groundwork for sustainable peace.

Despite their significant contributions, women continue to face barriers to their full and equal participation in peacebuilding efforts. These barriers include systemic discrimination, patriarchal norms, lack of access to resources and decision-making processes, and gender-based violence. Addressing these challenges is essential for harnessing the transformative potential of women's engagement in peacebuilding and realizing the goal of inclusive and sustainable peace.

Case studies illustrating the impact of women's involvement in conflict resolution

I. Liberia: Women of Liberia Mass Action for Peace (WOLMAP)⁸

During Liberia's devastating civil war (1989-2003), women bore the brunt of violence, displacement, and loss. In response to the conflict's devastation and the failure of political leaders to negotiate peace, women across religious and ethnic divides mobilized to demand an end to the fighting. Led by grassroots activist Leymah Gbowee and supported by women like Comfort Freeman and Vaiba Flomo, the Women of Liberia Mass Action for Peace (WOLMAP) emerged as a powerful force for change.

WOLMAP employed innovative tactics such as sit-ins, protests, and sex strikes to pressure warring factions into negotiating peace. They marched through the streets of Monrovia, dressed in white, singing songs of peace, and calling for an end to the violence. Their courageous actions captured the attention of the international community and forced the warring parties to take notice.

In 2003, their efforts culminated in the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Agreement, which ended the civil war and paved the way for democratic elections. Leymah Gbowee and other women leaders were instrumental in ensuring that women's voices were heard in the peace negotiations, leading to provisions for women's participation in the transitional government and the inclusion of gender-sensitive provisions in the peace agreement.

The impact of WOLMAP's activism extended beyond the signing of the peace agreement. Women played key roles in post-conflict reconstruction efforts, promoting reconciliation, healing war wounds, and rebuilding communities. Leymah Gbowee's leadership and advocacy for women's rights earned her the Nobel Peace Prize in 2011, further highlighting the transformative power of women's involvement in conflict resolution.

II. Northern Ireland: Northern Ireland Women's Coalition (NIWC)⁹

⁸ Koehnlein EM and others, 'From Conflict to Gender Quota Adoption: The Cases of Burundi and Liberia'

⁹ Cowell-Meyers KB, 'The Social Movement as Political Party: The Northern Ireland Women's Coalition and the Campaign for Inclusion'

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During the Northern Ireland conflict (1969-1998), known as "The Troubles," women played vital roles in community organizing, peacebuilding, and reconciliation efforts. In the aftermath of decades of sectarian violence, the Northern Ireland Women's Coalition (NIWC) emerged as a pioneering force for peace and democracy. Formed in 1996, the NIWC was a cross-community, feminist political party that sought to amplify women's voices in the peace process and promote gender equality in Northern Ireland. Led by women such as Monica McWilliams and Pearl Sagar, the NIWC advocated for inclusive dialogue, human rights, and social justice.

In the negotiations leading to the Good Friday Agreement in 1998, the NIWC played a crucial role in bridging sectarian divides and advocating for the inclusion of women's perspectives and priorities in the peace talks. Their emphasis on issues such as human rights, equality, and community reconciliation helped to address longstanding grievances and build consensus across political and religious divides. The Good Friday Agreement, which was endorsed by most Northern Ireland's citizens in a referendum, laid the foundation for a power-sharing government and marked the beginning of a new era of peace and stability in the region. The NIWC's legacy continues to inspire women's political participation and activism in Northern Ireland and beyond.

III. Columbia: Columbian Peace Process¹⁰

Through the peace negotiations conducted in Colombia, women had the opportunity to make the difference as very active peace-makers, representatives of the dialogue, and shapers of the peace agreement in-between the Government of Colombia and the Revolution Colombian Army (FARC). Among multivariate factors that were critical in peace negotiations was women's role, which helped to tackle the roots of the conflict such as gender-based violence, political marginalization, and social inequality. The women of Colombia, fuelled by their partisan origins as well as grassroots leaders from conflict-ridden communities, took a stand and joined in the negotiations with women from different ethnic, regional and socio-economic backgrounds. The role of women's organizations and networks that are active in the peace process, like Ruta Pacifica de las Mujeres and the Liga de Mujeres Desplazadas (League of Displaced Women), is undeniable in enticing gender dialogue and fostering the establishment of a gender sub-commission within the negotiation frame. The establishment of the gender-related sub-commission sought to ensure that gender issues were embedded into the peace talks process and such issues as women's rights, gender-based violence, among others, were comprehensively addressed. Achieving gender parity and empowering women in the peace process led to the accounting of gender-sensitive clauses into the Final Agreement which comprised protection for women's rights and basically care for the interests of women and girls who had been victims of the conflict.

Legal Frameworks Promoting Women's Participation in Conflict Resolution

I. *International legal instruments supporting women's rights in conflict resolution*

International law creates both a strong and comprehensive framework which is for the protection of women rights and providing them with an opportunity of influencing the crisis intervention processes. CEDAW (Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women)¹¹ comes as the foundation of the framework, was adopted by the General assembly of the United Nations in 1979. CEDAW requires states to prohibit discrimination against women and treating everyone fairly by ensuring their participation without exception in all activities, including conflict resolution. For instance, the United Nations Security

¹⁰ 'Innovations in the Colombian Peace Process', 'Innovations in the Colombian Peace Process' (1 June 2016)

¹¹ 'The CEDAW Effect: International Law's Impact on Women's Rights', 'The CEDAW Effect: International Law's Impact on Women's Rights' (6 March 2014)

Council Resolution 1325 (UNSCR 1325), passed in 2000 is a resolution that is the milestone because it acknowledges the distortion in which women suffer the most in conflicts and puts emphasis on their inclusion in peacebuilding and decision-making processes. UNSCR 1325 stresses the necessity for the greater participation of women in all conflict resolution processes concomitantly with the protection of women's rights and interests in and after armed conflicts. The involvement of women should be integrated into peacebuilding and post-conflict recovery strategies. Whereas the latter actions, such as UNSCR 1820, 1888, 1889, 1960, 2106, and 2122 reinforce the core principles by tackling problems related to sexual violence in war, women's involvement in peacekeeping mission, and protection of women and girls in humanitarian situations. Moreover, international humanitarian law embodying the Geneva Conventions and their Additional Protocols, bans gender-based violence and provides the women and girls with rights in situations of conflicts. Together, these legal instruments serve as an overall framework for promoting gender equality, protecting women's rights, and ensuring women's role as humanitarians into each peace and security situation globally. Through the acknowledging of women's individual experiences and meanings behind conflicts diplomacy law seeks to address the direct root that the conflicts come from, the building of more extensive and long-term inclusiveness and peace for all.

II. National laws and policies promoting gender equality in peacebuilding in India

In India inequality between men and women is the cornerstone of the rule of law and of the country's policies abroad as well as at home that contributes to the development of peacebuilding. The Constitution has provisions that respect fundamental rights and freedoms of people, for instance, equality before law (Article 14) and prohibition of gender-based discrimination (Article 15)¹², which forms basic foundations of recognizing gender disparity and works to guarantee equal opportunities for women in all areas of life including peace building initiatives. Also, part IV of the Constitution – The Principles of Directive Policy of State (DPSP) – signifies the state's dedication to social justice and equality, Article 39 (a) demanding that state guarantees that women and men and men and women enjoy an equal status. Furthermore, discrimination shall be based on sex, forbidden. The law in law such as the act of protection of women from domestic violence, passed in 2005 and the act of sexual harassment of woman at workplace (prevention, prohibition, and redressal) act of 2013 are a solid performance of India's efforts in agitating gender-based violence and making an enabling environment for women's contribution in peacebuilding exercises. Adding to this, the affirmative action policies including the clause of reservations for women in state constituency assemblies as the representation of women in the grassroot level decision making aims at to increase the involvement of women in peacebuilding initiatives.

III. United Nations Security Council Resolutions on Women, Peace, and Security

United Nations Security Council Resolutions (UNSCRs) on Women, Peace, and Security which represent a sensitive framework to ensure the promotion of gender equality and women's empowerment in conflict prevention, resolution, and reconstruction, is one and a half years to end the war, all over the world. In 2000, the UNSCR 1325 was approved and the scope of these resolutions began expanding with recognition to the fact that conflict tends to affect women more than men.¹³ Also, the need for women to actually play a role in peace negotiations was highlighted. UNSCR 1325 is referring to the need to provide opportunities for women to be in the leadership positions and the peace and security-related power structures which require member states to first and foremost ensure their presence in every stage of conflict resolution and

¹² Bhatia G, 'Horizontal Discrimination and Article 15(2) of the Indian Constitution: A Transformative Approach'

¹³ 'Negotiations at the UN: The Case of UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace and Security' pp 239

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peacebuilding. Afterwards, numerous modifications were introduced in the subsequent resolutions such as the UNSCRs 1820, 1888, 1889, 1960, 2106, and 2122 that served to reinforce the above principles and expand the coverage of the Women, Peace, and Security agenda in order to deal with the perpetual problems of sexual violence in conflict. In turn, these resolutions highlight the relevance of integrating gender dimensions into all spheres of peace initiatives, including ceasefire agreements, peace negotiation meetings, and post conflict reconstruction programs.

Mechanisms for Enhancing Women's Involvement

Mechanisms for enhancing women's involvement include implementing quota systems and affirmative action measures to ensure their representation in decision-making bodies, providing capacity-building programs tailored to women's needs, developing gender-responsive policies and programs, enacting supportive legal frameworks that protect women's rights, conducting awareness-raising and advocacy campaigns to challenge stereotypes and promote positive attitudes towards women's leadership, and fostering networking and collaboration among stakeholders to amplify women's voices and drive collective action towards gender equality goals. These mechanisms collectively contribute to creating inclusive and equitable societies where women have equal opportunities and representation across all sectors.

I. Quota systems and affirmative action measures in the context of Indian Constitution

Within the context of the Indian Constitution, there can be no doubt that selections based on quota systems and the enforcement of affirmative action are essential tools for enhancing the active role of women and their representation across many sectors of society. The Constitution of India enlists comprehensive approaches to upholding equity and enhancing social justice, through among others special provisions designed to nullify the effects of historical injustices and to empower the disenfranchised population that includes women. Article 15 (I) prohibits discrimination using sex as a criterion but allows for enactment of specific laws to uplift women and children as the people who need policy intervention more.¹⁴ This constitutional clause is the foundation for the implementation of quota systems through which women gain the opportunity to acquire higher social status and participate in governance, education, employment, etc. One of the instances where this is seen is found in Section 243D and 243T where women seats are set aside in local government bodies as stated in the Indian constitution. These mandates oblige a given share of the Panchayat and Municipal seats to be allocated to personally male candidates. The quota of seats is state-specific and they mostly stand either between 33-50%. This seat is an attempt to increase the representation of women and participate them in the local decision-making processes thus, make them visibly and vocal effective participants in their communities so that also contribute in social and overall development.

II. Capacity-building programs for women in conflict-affected areas

Women capacity building in conflict-affected areas in the interest of both India nationally and the world at large is important because and women can be the agents of the peace process and the conflict resolution process. In India, implementation of such programs becomes instrumental in the efforts to address the special needs of women in a conflict area, where they are mostly vulnerable and can be victims of violence, displacement, and social stigmatization. These endeavours may involve a spectrum of actions such as offering women training in peacebuilding, mediation, negotiation, leadership, and empowerment of the community. Training women with

¹⁴ Nanivadekar M, 'Are Quotas a Good Idea? the Indian Experience with Reserved Seats for Women'

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the necessary know-how and skills to participate in peace negotiations capacitates them to push for their interests, solve grievances, and foster social integrations in their communities.¹⁵

III. Civil society initiatives advocating for women's inclusion in peace processes

Civil society initiatives directed towards enhancing Indian women's participation in peace processes is a vital link in a chain where women have hardly had a say in the formal decision-making forums that address the issues related to conflict resolution and peace building in the past. Many important projects have been established in several parts of the country, whose purpose is to enhance women's voices, to defend their rights, in addition to adopt gender-sensitive approaches to peace and security.¹⁶ One example is a women's regional network (WRN) that is operational in zones of conflicts such as Jammu and Kashmir, North-east India, and other regions affected by Naxal insurgency. It the Women's Role in Negotiations (WRN) that unites women from varied backgrounds including survivors of violence, activists, and community leaders to find strategies for gender-sensitive peacebuilding. By means of the workshops, advocacy activities, and dialogue forums, the WRN equips women to take part in the mediation process and exercise influence by policy makers. Similarly, the WRN is the platform which bring together women from Jammu and Kashmir and government officials in a conversation where they discuss the issues that are most pressing such as human rights violations, gender-based trauma and the implications of the conflict on women's lives.

Suggestions and Future directions for research and policy development in promoting women's participation in peacebuilding efforts

Reinforcement of legal system to support women engagement, refiling of education and training programmes for women with peace-building capacities, as well as assurance of security and safety of women in peacebuilding efforts will decisively play the role of policy recommendations for attaining gender equality and empowering women in peacebuilding processes. Through the below mentioned recommendations a matter of priority, governments, NGOs and international community can create the environment that will allow women to play their major role in peacebuilding and address the root causes of the conflicts and build durable and sustainable peace in their communities and beyond.

- I. **Long-Term Impact Assessment:** Longitudinal studies should be conducted to determine the long-term effect of women's peacebuilding as one of the birds of their peace-making efforts. The research is assigned to the processes of gender mainstreaming establishment assessment, adjustment of the gender statuses, and control of peace outcome longevity.
- II. **Intersectionality and Inclusivity:** Discussing how the overlap or interloping of various identities (for instance: race, ethnicity, class, sex) factor into women's experiences in conflict and peaceful resolution. Future studies should apply a multilateral approach to the study of how discrimination is manifested in various forms converge and affect the presence of women in peace processes, thus ensuring the equality and consideration of those in the margins of the society.
- III. **Innovative Financing Mechanisms:** Moreover, constructing novel financing models that help to address the participation of women in peace building initiatives. Policy makers need to try some alternative models of financing that focus on gender budgeting, gender impact investment and public-private partnerships for women peace

¹⁵ 'Health Research Capacity Building of Health Workers in Fragile and Conflict-affected Settings: A Scoping Review of Challenges, Strengths, and Recommendations' (2021) 19 84

¹⁶ Paffenholz T, 'Civil Society and Peace Negotiations: Beyond the Inclusion-exclusion Dichotomy'

builders' capacitation and fundraising so as to finance these initiatives in a sustainable matrix.

- IV. **Capacity Building and Training:** Fortifying the training programs for women on the basis of peace building skills, leadership promotion and advocacy. In the context of the future initiative, women's technical skills trainings, negotiation, and mediation trainings, as well as self-confidence to participate in the negotiation processes should be enhanced.
- V. **Technology and Digital Innovation:** Leveraging technology, digital transformation, and women's involvement in peacebuilding processes in conflict zones. Research should be able to identify the strengths and weakness of digital tools, social media and online networking in women perception of amplifying their voices, facilitating information sharing and mobilizing supports for peace initiatives in conflict-affected areas.

Conclusion

Broadening the participation of women in peacebuilding activities is necessary for the development of multilateral, enduring and stable peace practices by putting both gender mainstreaming and essential finances in place. Gender mainstreaming is the tool that allows to identify and respond to the particular gender as well as age-based needs and issues of the parties' conflict-affected during all stages of peacebuilding.¹⁷ Using gender-sensitivity in conflict analysis, program-design and implementation, the governments and organizations can craft special and tailored interventions that implement gender equality and women empowerment. Financial resources and differentiated resources allocation that would enable women to truly contribute to peacebuilding process are the main enablers to this effect. Supporting women-led initiatives, peacebuilding projects, and development of their skills will be a good starting point for their participation in decision-making processes, fostering their leadership abilities, and finally, contributing to a longer lasting peace in the region. As I look forward, it is very important to make women come first in terms of peacebuilding approaches including the setting of policies and programs, set aside relevant resources to support inclusion of women, and boost research and policy on this field. By forsaking gender discriminations, strengthening women representation and encouraging binding peace processes, the stakeholders will achieve a world that is just, equitable and enduring for everyone.¹⁸

¹⁷ Cahill-Ripley A, 'Reclaiming the Peacebuilding Agenda: Economic and Social Rights as a Legal Framework for Building Positive Peace - A Human Security Plus Approach to Peacebuilding' (2016) 16 223

¹⁸ Schnabel A and Tabyshalieva A, *Defying Victimhood: Women and Post-conflict Peacebuilding* (2012)